

SOME ASPECTS OF CHILDREN'S RIGHTS PROTECTION

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Abstract. The article analyzes international and national regulations on the protection of the rights and freedoms of children, the measures taken in our country to ensure the rights of the child. Opinions were expressed on the responsibilities and obligations of the state, as well as parents or guardians in the development of a harmoniously developed generation.

Key words: child, upbringing, child's rights, normative legal act, obligation.

Аннотация. Мақолада болаларнинг ҳуқуқ ва эркинликларини ҳимоя қилишга оид халқаро ва миллий норматив-ҳуқуқий ҳужжатлар, мамлакатимизда бола ҳуқуқларини таъминлаш бўйича амалга оширилаётган чора-тадбирлар таҳлил қилинган. Баркамол авлодни камол топтиришда давлат, шунингдек ота-оналар ёки уларнинг ўрнини босувчи шахслар зиммасидаги масъулият ва мажбурият тўғрисида фикр-мулоҳазалар билдирилган.

Калит сўзлар: бола, тарбия, бола ҳуқуқлари, норматив-ҳуқуқий ҳужжат, мажбурият.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются международные и национальные нормативные акты по защите прав и свобод детей, меры, принимаемые в нашей стране для обеспечения прав ребенка.

Ключевые слова: ребенок, воспитание, права ребенка, нормативно-правовой акт, обязанность.

Protecting the rights of children in our country has been and still is one of the most pressing issues. It will remain so in the future, because children are the force that determines the future of the nation, the people, the state.

Every state that aims to build a civil society must be based on democratic principles, first of all, it means that this process will go a long way, and focuses on the protection of children's rights and their upbringing. The upbringing of worthy heirs will contribute to the development of society in the realization of this lofty goal, which embodies the noble aspirations of the

people. The words of the great enlightener Abdullah Avloni, "Education is for us a matter of life or death, salvation or destruction, happiness or disaster"¹, have not lost their significance for our nation at the beginning of the century.

Therefore, ensuring their rights and freedoms in society is important in educating a harmoniously developed young generation.

The policy on protecting the interests of children in each country should be based on information about the real situation of children, ways to better meet their needs.

¹ Avloni, Abdullah. Selected works: 2 volumes, 2nd edition, 2 volumes. Teachings, examples, stories, life of prophets, dramas, articles, travel memories // Editorial Board: N.Karimov et al .; Collector: B.Kasimov; Comments and dictionary compiled by O.Tulabaev /. - T .: "Manaviyat", 2006. - B-37.

According to the Internet, about 250 million children around the world work instead of studying, 5.7 million children are involved in forced labor, more than 70 million children do not go to school, 1.8 million children are involved in prostitution or pornography, one child becomes a victim of human trafficking². These numbers themselves show us how important it is to protect the rights of children and ensure their safety.

According to the data, 36.6% (12,157,063 people) of the population are children (0-18 years old), of which 51.7% (6,279,778 people) are boys and 48.3% (5,877,285 people) are girls. Also, according to the analysis of children by age, 10.7% of them are 0–4 years old, 9.6% are 5–9 years old, 8.6% are 10–14 years old, and 7.7% are 15–18 years old³.

Based on these figures, it can be said that children are a key force influencing and deciding the future development of society and the state. From time immemorial, our people have always paid special attention to the provision, education and training of children, the acquisition of a profession, and, in general, the development of a mature person, demonstrating the qualities of childhood.

As a result of the fact that the upbringing of children begins at birth and continues, children are required to instill in them the spirit of regular observance of the rules established in society and voluntary obedience to the laws.

Caring for a child from birth, ensuring a healthy and proper upbringing and modern education is our duty to the children who are the future of our society, the foundation of our future. The reason is that children are like pure water. It is no secret that no matter what container the water is placed in, it takes the form of that container, and children perceive the environment, the manners and behavior of parents and caregivers exactly as they see it. It is no coincidence that the saying, “He does what he sees in the bird’s nest”⁴.

The legal framework for the protection of the rights of the child is a set of normative and legal

documents that define the policy of protection of children's rights and freedoms in society, regulating social relations arising in the process of its implementation, defining the rights and obligations of participants and preventive activities⁵.

Therefore, international regulations on the protection of the rights and freedoms of children have been joined. These are: the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948); “Minimum Standard Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners” (1957); International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (1966); International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (1965); Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (1979); Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (1984); “Declaration of Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime and Abuse of Power” (1985); United Nations Rules for the Protection of Minors in Prison (1986); “A set of principles for the protection of all persons detained in any form or in prison” (1988); Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989); “The code of conduct for law enforcement officials is effective guidelines for higher education” (1989); United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for Non-Imprisonment Measures (Tokyo Rules) (1990); “Basic Principles of Treatment of Prisoners” (1990); “Basic Principles of the Use of Force and Firearms by Law Enforcement Officials” (1990); “United Nations Program Principles for the Prevention of Juvenile Delinquency (Riyadh Program Principles)” (1990); “Additional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child against Trafficking in Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography (2000); Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2006); The Declaration on the Protection of Children Victims of Crime and Witnesses to Crime (2005) and other similar normative legal acts.

The only mechanism for legal regulation that incorporates legislation in various areas of the rights of the child is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child” of 7

² <http://www.jeevajyothi.org>.

³ 2010-2020 State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Demography. Population and vitality statistics / www.stat.uz (19.02.2020).

⁴ Yodgorov H., Deputy Chairman of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Chairman of the Judicial Board for Civil Cases / Why do minors commit crimes? kun.uz / Society: 02.03.2018.

⁵ Ismoilov I., Ziyodullaev M., Isroilova N., Azimova F. Prevention of juvenile delinquency and delinquency: Textbook / Editor-in-Chief I. Ismailov. - T., 2011. - B-10.

January 2008, which sets out the basic principles and provisions of the Convention on the Rights of the Child. This law can be called the Children's Constitution, which strengthens the whole set of children's rights enshrined in the above-mentioned Convention.

According to Articles 43-45 of the Convention, the UN Committee on the Rights of the Child, consisting of 10 experts, has been established. The experts shall be elected by the States Parties to the Convention for a term of four years (with the right of re-election), taking into account the fair geographical distribution and the general legal system.

The Committee may request information from Member States on the extent to which they are complying with the requirements of the Convention and on the actual situation of children in the country, must collect and analyze information on the situation of children in different countries, develop relevant recommendations and submit a report to the UN General Assembly every two years through ECOSOC with its proposals and recommendations. The Committee works closely with UN specialized agencies (ILO, WHO, etc.), UNICEF and other UN agencies, governments and NGOs.

Specific protection: According to UNICEF, in more than 40 countries, national and regional child's rights representation services serve as an independent mechanism for ensuring children's rights.

Efforts by the United Nations, such as declaring 1979 the International Year of the Child, underscore the importance of children's rights and the need to establish mechanisms to monitor their observance.

The protection of children's rights is ensured through international covenants on civil and political, economic, social and cultural rights, as well as universal instruments such as the Convention on the Rights of the Child, adopted unanimously by the UN General Assembly on 20 November 1989.

More than twenty countries around the world have incorporated the principles of the Convention on the Rights of the Child into their Constitutions.

A law was adopted "On Accession of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on Child Trafficking, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography" (New York, May 25, 2000)⁶ and the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child (New York, May 25, 2000)⁷.

In addition, over the past three years, the country has adopted a number of normative and legal acts aimed at improving the system of guarantees for the rights of the child, especially children in need of social protection, in particular, orphans and children deprived of parental care, and systematic measures are being taken⁸.

These normative and legal acts set the task of forming a completely new system for the care of children, including children in need of protection, in particular, orphans and children deprived of parental care, to ensure their social and legal protection.

The focus on the rights of the child in the Republic of Uzbekistan is primarily due to the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, Article 45 of the Constitution states that the rights of minors, the disabled and the lonely elderly are under the protection of the state, and the duty to protect the material interests of minors is established.

Special care and qualified medical care should be provided to children with disabilities and orphans so that they can find their place in society and not be oppressed. The child has the right to education, to have an adequate standard of living for physical, mental, spiritual and social development. It is the high responsibility placed on parents, above all, to fulfill those requirements. Education, based on the physical and mental abilities of the child, should serve to form his consciousness, to find his place in society. In accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the state guarantees the child's freedom of thought, speech and religion, the right to rest, freedom of scientific and technical creativity, and the right to enjoy cultural achievements. Consequently, Article 64 of the Constitution stipulates that parents are obliged

⁶ Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2008, No. 50, Article 492.

⁷ Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2008, No. 50, Article 494

⁸ No. PP-4185 of 11 February 2019 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Additional Measures to Strengthen Social Protection of Orphans and Children Deprived of Parental Care"; No. PP-4296 of April 22, 2019 "On Additional Measures to Further Strengthen the Guarantees of the Rights of the Child"; Resolutions No. PP-4736 of May 29, 2020 "On additional measures to improve the system of protection of the rights of the child" and the normative legal acts adopted in the framework of their implementation.

to care for and educate their children until they reach adulthood, and that the state and society provide for the care, upbringing and education of orphans and children deprived of parental care, encourage charitable activities. The requirements are being met by our state.

In addition to the fact that the Constitution stipulates that parents are obliged to support and educate their children until they reach adulthood, the able-bodied adult child also establishes the procedure for caring for their parents. Accordingly, Article 66 of the Constitution sets norms on the obligation of able-bodied children to take care of their parents, and in order to ensure the practical application of these norms, Article 47⁵ of the Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for incapacitated a financial assistance. Refusal to provide financial support to a needy parent or their surrogate, ie failure to pay the amount required for their financial support by a court decision for a total of more than two months – administrative detention for a period of fifteen days or this Code shall result in a fine of twenty times the minimum wage to persons who cannot be subjected to appropriate administrative detention. A person who has committed an offense for the first time shall be released from liability if he has voluntarily paid the alimony debt in the course of hearing an administrative offense case⁹. Article 123 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that adults who refuse to provide financial support to their parents or guardians who are incapable of work and in need of financial assistance, ie the amount to be collected by a court decision for non-payment for a longer period, if committed after the imposition of an administrative penalty for such an act - is punishable by up to three years of correctional labor or up to one year of imprisonment, if the person

has paid the alimony debt in full, he is released from liability.

In conclusion, the state and parents or their surrogates have a number of responsibilities in ensuring the rights of children in order to raise a mature, harmoniously developed generation in the family until they reach adulthood.

These obligations include:

first, to provide the child with shelter, seasonal clothing, and adequate food;

second, to protect the child from various dangers that endanger his life and health;

third, to conduct regular medical examinations and physical training for the child to grow up harmoniously, paying attention to the child's health as well as the proper development of his body;

fourth, the traditions inherited from our ancestors to the child by providing a high spiritual environment in the family (kindness, sincerity, care, respect for the elder, the younger, greetings, hospitality, friendship, solidarity, love, humanity, etc.) and inculcating a spirit of morality;

fifth, to ensure that the child learns the secrets of learning, reading, writing, arithmetic, memorization in general education schools;

sixth, to support the child on a regular basis, to encourage and teach him a trade;

seventh, to instill in the child immunity against foreign ideas and to help him develop feelings of love, honor, pride, and affection for the Motherland, national and religious values, customs and culture.

By effectively fulfilling the above-mentioned responsibilities, the state, parents or their surrogates will not only ensure the rights of children and form a mature, harmonious generation in the family, but also ensure their future well-being.

⁹ National database of the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 10.01.2018, No. 03/18/459/0536 - 3-m.